

Classification of Cardiac Arrhythmias Using CNN-LSTM Networks and Wide Features

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Abstract

Cardiac arrhythmias are an essential challenge for clinical diagnosis and treatment; accurate and efficient classification methods are necessary to ensure precision. This study proposes a novel approach using deep-learning methods on 12-lead Electrocardiogram (ECG) recordings to classify cardiac abnormalities. Our approach merges a CNN Long Short-Term Memory (CNN-LSTM) network with static features to classify the 12-lead ECG. Our method uses the raw ECG waveforms as input to CNN to comprise the ECG waveforms, which are then fed to the LSTM network. Then, a set of 64 automatically learned features from the CNN-LSTM network merged with static ECG features. Experimental studies have been performed for nine different types of heartbeats obtained from the CPSC2018 dataset. These nine types are Normal Sinus Rhythm (NSR), Right Bundle Branch Block (RBBB), Atrial Fibrillation (AF), 1st Degree Av Block (IAVB), Premature Ventricular Contractions (PVC), Left Bundle Branch Block (LBBB), Premature Atrial Contraction (PAC), ST Depression (STD), and ST Elevation (STE). We got an Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic (AUROC) score of 0.9324. Our findings highlight the effectiveness of applying deep learning architectures and static ECG features for accurate and clinically relevant arrhythmia classification. This research contributes to advancing the field of cardiac diagnostics and offers a promising way to improve the efficiency and accuracy of arrhythmia detection in clinical practice.

Keywords: CNN-LSTM, Deep Learning, Static Features, ECG recordings

Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases lead to death globally [1]. According to the World Health Organization, cardiovascular diseases were responsible for death of 32% in 2019, causing nearly 17.9 million deaths. Heart arrhythmia or irregular heartbeat is caused by abnormal intracardiac conduction or pulse formation that affects the speed or rhythm of the heart [2]. The 12-lead electrocardiogram (ECG) is a comprehensive representation of the electrical signaling activity of the human heart to evaluate its condition and diagnose cardiac abnormalities [3]. Manual interpretation of 12-lead ECG is time-consuming and requires skilled personnel, so the automatic detection of cardiac abnormalities through 12-lead ECG recordings has a reliable clinical diagnostic value for arrhythmia [4].

Since the late 1950s, automatic algorithms for ECG interpretation have improved due to advancements in computational capacity and the development of new methods for analysis, preprocessing, and classification [5]. Algorithms typically consist of three main processes: feature extraction, feature selection, and classification. These processes analyze data and identify and classify relevant features [6]. Using machine learning methods like convolutional neural networks (CNN) eliminates the need for previously defined features and can take raw or preprocessed signals as input [7].

Numerous deep neural network architectures have been proposed for the automated analysis of electrocardiograms (ECGs). These methods have been successful in accurately detecting pathologies in clinical settings. However, existing studies lack comprehensive comparisons across multiple types of heart abnormalities. They focus on a single or few combinations, such as atrial fibrillation, while some have studied ST changes. To address this issue, the China Physiological Signal Challenge 2018 (CPSC 2018) introduced a more comprehensive database [8]. The CPSC 2018 dataset comprises one standard ECG type and eight abnormal ECG types. In this study, we propose a multilabel classification algorithm that fuses a convolutional neural plus long short-term memory (CNN+LSTM) network with a concatenation of static features for the automated, comprehensive interpretation of the ECG.

Dataset

The dataset used in this study was obtained from the China Physiological Signaling Competition (CPSC) 2018 [8]. CPSC 2018 presented a comprehensive platform for sharing data and algorithms focused on analyzing physiological signals to identify rhythm and morphology abnormalities in 12-lead electrocardiograms (ECGs). The main goal was to facilitate the development and evaluation of anomaly detection methods. The dataset includes records from 11 hospitals across China. While the publicly available training set contained 6877 ECG records, each tape recording is presented in MATLAB format and consists of the patient's demographic information, such as gender and age, as well as ECG information. Recordings are categorized into nine types, including one standard type and eight abnormal types: atrial fibrillation (AF), First-degree atrioventricular block (I-AVB), Left bundle branch block (LBBB), Right bundle branch block (RBBB), premature atrial contraction (PAC), premature ventricular contraction (PVC), ST segment depression (STD) and, ST-segment elevation (STE). In particular, the recording of the ECG signal was sampled at 500 Hz, providing high-resolution data for analysis. Table 1 shows the details of the dataset.

Table 1. Data profile

No	Type	Total recording	Mean Time Length (s)
1	Normal	918	15.43
2	AF	1098	15.01
3	I-AVB	704	14.32
4	LBBB	207	14.92
5	RBBB	1695	14.42
6	PAC	574	19.46
7	PVC	653	20.21
8	STD	826	15.13
9	STE	202	17.15
#	Total/Average	6877	15.79

Preprocessing

All recorded ECGs underwent a standard preprocessing process before training. First, down sampled the signal to 100Hz to reduce the input size and computational time. Then the process included applying a bandpass filter with a bandwidth between 1 Hz and 45 Hz to isolate important heart frequencies and eliminate noise. Additionally, every recording was normalized to ensure a consistent signal amplitude across the dataset. To maintain uniformity, a fixed window size of 1600 points was used for recordings that varied in length, and a zero layer was added to records shorter than this length. These preprocessing steps were performed to improve signal quality, reduce confounding factors, and facilitate efficient model training.

Model Architecture

The proposed model architecture comprises two primary components: static feature extraction and deep feature extraction.

Static Feature Extraction

The first lead of the electrocardiogram (ECG) signals was used to extract features. These features included the amplitude and duration of P-, Q-, R-, S-, and T waves for each beat. Summary statistics, such as mean, median, and standard deviation, were calculated for the amplitude and duration of each wave. PR, QS, RT interval times, and P-wave energy were also calculated for each model [9]. In total, 140 static features were extracted from the template data. To identify the most informative features, a random forest algorithm was used to rank the extracted features. The best 16 features were selected to be included in the final model. Additionally, gender and age were added, resulting in 18 fixed features in the final fully connected layer. Table 2 shows the top 16 features of the random forest algorithm identified, providing insights into the key factors contributing to the model's prediction performance.

Deep Feature Extraction

The proposed model for electrocardiogram (ECG) signal classification combines convolutional neural network (CNN) and short-term memory (LSTM) layers for deep feature extraction. This approach is inspired by a previous work that used transformers for a similar purpose [10]. However, we used LSTM layers instead of transformers to capture temporal dependencies in ECG signals.

The CNN component of our model consists of multiple convolution layers that operate on 12-lead ECG signals. It extracts spatial information and identifies relevant patterns that indicate heart abnormalities. Each convolution layer is followed by batch normalization and modified linear unit (ReLU) activation to extract increasingly abstract features. Table 3 lists the details for each convolution layer.

Unlike the transformer-based approach in the referenced work, our model uses LSTM layers to process the encoded sequence from the CNN layers. The LSTM layer module combines multiple LSTM layers to capture temporal and long-term dependencies within the input sequence. This choice was made to take advantage of LSTM's strengths in modeling sequential data and capturing the subtle temporal dynamics present in ECG signals.

Afterward, a fully connected layer is added to produce the deep features. The process involves combining the static and deep features and then applying a final fully connected layer to match the number of prediction classes. This combination allows the model to capture basic signal properties, complex temporal dynamics, and contextual information. By integrating static and deep features, the model can leverage the inherent properties of learned signals and representations, ultimately improving the performance of the classification task. You can find a visual representation of the model's structure in Figure 1, and Table 4 shows the selected hyper-parameters.

Table 2. Top 16 features as discovered from a Random Forest model

No	Feature Name	No	Feature Name
1	S wave amp	9	P wave eng
2	PR time	10	Template swt med power ratio
3	ST time	11	QRS energy higuchi fractal dimension
4	P wave time	12	P wave amp
5	T wave sample entropy median	13	Template swt a_4 med power ratio
6	T wave eng	14	QRS pearson p-value
7	T wave hurst exponent std	15	Template swt a_1 low power ratio
8	QRS energy pearson coeff	16	Rpeak hurst exponent

Table 3. Convolution layer details

Conv. Layer	Input size	Output size	Kernel size	Stride	Padding
1	12	128	10	2	1
2	128	256	8	2	0
3	256	256	6	1	0
4	256	256	6	1	0

Table 4. Hyper-parameters for classification of ECG recording using static and deep models.

Hyper-Parameter	Value	Hyper-Parameter	Value
ECG Window size (points)	8000	Number of LSTM layer	4
Sampling frequency (Hz)	500	Number of LSTM neurons	128
Batch size	128	Embedding size CNN	256
Static feature size	18	FC 1 Size	64
Deep feature size	64	FC 2 Size	9
Number of classes	9	Dropout	0.2

Figure 1. Visually Model Architecture

Result

The performance of the proposed model was extensively evaluated using the cross-entropy loss function, Adam optimizer, and AUROC (Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristic curve) metric. To ensure robustness and reliability, we employed 10-fold cross-validation. This involved dividing the dataset into 10 subsets, utilizing 8 folds for training, one for testing, and one for validation. The model demonstrated promising results, achieving an overall test AUROC score of 0.9324 and a validation AUROC score of 0.9358. Table 5 shows the validation and test results for overall and each fold. These scores reflect the model's ability to effectively discriminate between cardiac abnormalities based on the extracted features from the electrocardiogram (ECG) signals. The high AUROC scores indicate strong performance in sensitivity and specificity, demonstrating the model's capability to accurately classify abnormal ECG patterns while minimizing false positives and negatives. This performance is particularly noteworthy given the complexity and variability of ECG signals, highlighting the effectiveness of the proposed model architecture in capturing relevant features for classification. The utilization of 10-fold cross-validation enhances the robustness of the results by reducing the impact of dataset variability and ensuring that the model's performance is consistent across different subsets of the data. This comprehensive evaluation strategy provides confidence in the generalization ability of the model and its potential utility in real-world clinical settings. The achieved AUROC scores signify significant advancements in detecting and classifying cardiac abnormalities, offering promise for enhancing diagnostic accuracy and patient care.

Table 5. The result for the Test and Validation set in AUROC

Test Set	AUROC	Validation Set	AUROC
0	0.9401	9	0.9419
1	0.9302	0	0.9372
2	0.9325	1	0.9281
3	0.9319	2	0.9419
4	0.9374	3	0.9404
5	0.9271	4	0.9432
6	0.9307	5	0.9281
7	0.9350	6	0.9313
8	0.9257	7	0.9373
9	0.9336	8	0.9287
Mean:	0.9324	Mean:	0.9358

Conclusion

This study introduces a new model architecture for detecting and classifying cardiac abnormalities using electrocardiogram (ECG) signals. The model integrates static features extracted from template data with deep features obtained through a combination of convolutional neural network (CNN) and long short-term memory (LSTM) layers. Our model demonstrates robust performance in discriminating between various cardiac conditions, supported by 10-fold cross-validation and rigorous evaluation metrics such as AUROC. The obtained AUROC scores of 0.9324 for the test set and 0.9358 for the validation set underscore the model's effectiveness in accurately identifying abnormal ECG patterns while minimizing false positives and negatives. These results have significant clinical implications, highlighting the importance of accurate and timely detection of cardiac abnormalities for early intervention and improved patient outcomes. The proposed model offers a promising tool for assisting healthcare professionals in diagnosing cardiovascular diseases, facilitating prompt treatment, and reducing the burden on healthcare systems. Future research efforts may focus on refining the model architecture, exploring alternative feature representations, and validating the approach on more extensive and diverse datasets. This study contributes to the growing body of literature on artificial intelligence-driven approaches for cardiovascular disease detection, underscoring the potential of advanced machine learning techniques to revolutionize healthcare delivery and improve patient outcomes in cardiac care.

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